

Monitoring the ion population at a carbon electrode/aqueous electrolyte interface at various pHs using electrochemical dilatometry

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ABSTRACT

Changes in the electrode thickness in electrochemical capacitors depend strongly on the electrolyte pH. Hence, different ions (or ions with various solvation shells) participate in electrical double-layer formation. In this study, *operando* electrochemical dilatometry experiments incorporating various electrochemical techniques, including cyclic voltammetry, large amplitude sinusoidal voltammetry, and step potential electrochemical spectroscopy, were performed on ECs operating in 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ with different pHs (6, 9, and 12) and 1 mol L⁻¹ LiOH (for comparative purposes). A microporous carbon (Kuraray YP-80F) was used as the electrode material. Comparable trends for the cell behaviour were observed for electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9; however, the cell containing the pH 12 solution exhibited similar behaviour to that containing the LiOH solution, suggesting that during positive polarization, the primary role was played by OH⁻, because the same salt concentration was used in all cases. This result raises an essential concern regarding the actual ion population at the electrode/electrolyte interface, which affects the water decomposition potentials and triggers various parasitic reactions impacting long-term electrochemical capacitor performance.

1. Introduction

An increase in energy consumption in recent years has driven considerable interest in energy harvesting, conversion, and storage devices. To realize sustainable development, there is a trend towards searching for environmentally friendly solutions in response to the depletion of natural resources and environmental issues [1–4]. For example, lithium is often replaced by sodium or potassium in batteries [5–8], and aqueous solutions are used instead of organic solutions as electrolytes in electrochemical capacitors (ECs) [9–14]. Making progress in materials research for ECs requires extensive fundamental knowledge and insightful studies, but simply developing materials with promising metrics is not adequate. The key is to tailor the properties of an electrode material to the electrolytic solution used. Considerations of the pore diameter vs. the size and number of ions at the interface are crucial for improving device performance. Hence, a comprehensive description of ionic fluxes at the electrode/electrolyte interface during polarization has considerable importance. There are numerous reports in the literature rationalizing the fading of EC performance, shortening of cycle life, or increased self-discharge under different medium and operating conditions [15–18]. Various research pathways, including the use of different

techniques, can be taken in performing fundamental studies on the interface between a carbon electrode and an electrolytic solution, as well as to elucidate the ageing mechanisms in ECs. A sophisticated approach is quite often employed in such studies: recently, *postmortem* analyses have been coupled with in situ experiments [19–26]. Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) [27–29], X-ray neutron scattering [30–32], Raman spectroscopy [12,33], atomic force microscopy (AFM) [34,35], electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance (EQCM) [22, 36–41], and electrochemical dilatometry (ECD) [20,27,42–46] are powerful techniques that provide insightful information on charge storage in ECs. However, most papers have been published on ionic liquid-based systems (ILs) or organic-electrolyte-based systems. It has been found that during EC charging, cations are indeed adsorbed at the negative electrode, whereas a more complex mechanism is operational at the positive electrode. The ion-mixing effect, i.e., cation desorption coupled with anion adsorption, is observed at low potential values (near the so-called point of zero charge PZC). In the case of water-based electrolytes, the potential range of ion mixing depends on both the electrolyte composition and the electrode material used (in terms of the accessible surface area and pore size distribution). Anion adsorption is considered to occur upon further increasing the potential, which plays

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an important role in electrode charge balancing; however, cations are still expelled from the material pores or the electrode surface [20,22,27,47-49]. Changes in the charge storage mechanism during electrode polarization are clearly reflected in volumetric changes of the electrode. The solvent has a pronounced effect on the volumetric changes of the electrode in an organic medium, where the larger the solvent molecules are, the higher the electrode expansion is [42,43]. Note that the solvent effect is considerably more pronounced for a negatively polarized electrode than for a positively polarized electrode. However, solvent molecules have been detected in material pores regardless of the direction of polarization [43]. These results indicate the significant impact of the electrolyte pH on the ionic fluxes and charge storage mechanism for aqueous-based ECs.

The charge storage and ionic fluxes at a porous electrode/aqueous electrolyte interface are affected by many factors, among which the electrolyte pH is one of the most important. It has been claimed that in a pH-neutral electrolytic solution, the maximum operating voltage of the cell can be increased above the theoretical voltage for water decomposition (1.23 V). Extreme pHs negatively impact current collectors; corrosion is expected at low pHs, whereas a passive layer can introduce an additional resistive component at high pHs. In both cases, current flow between the current collector and the electrode is impeded, resulting in high cell resistance. The aforementioned issues deteriorate the cycle life of ECs. However, note that even under relatively mild conditions (pHs between 6 and 9), local pH changes in nearly polarized electrodes affect the performance and shorten the life of ECs [50]. Variations in the concentrations of protons (H^+) and hydroxide anions (OH^-) can significantly impact the charge storage mechanism because the dissolution of salt produces ions that can act as charge carriers. Interestingly, the results of EQCM experiments showed that in an EC operating in an acidic electrolyte, protons H^+ , that is, hydrated protons (H_3O^+) [51,52], contribute to the electrode charge balance [22,47]. A similar effect was observed for alkaline electrolytes: the charge at the positively polarized electrode was (partially) balanced by OH^- anions [22].

Considering that the concentrations of H^+ and OH^- are definitely lower than the concentrations of dissolved salt in an electrolyte solution, electrode charge balancing by cations and anions derived from the salt used should be considered. The outstanding ionic mobility of H^+ and OH^- results in a significant contribution to charge storage. Theoretically, for the considered ions present below (Fig. 1), the smaller an ion is, the stronger its interactions with water molecules are; hence, many water molecules are strongly attracted to small ions so their hydrated diameter increases significantly if compared to the diameter of bare ion [53]. Fig. 1 is a comparison of the ionic diameters and ion mobilities for H^+ against lithium (Li^+) cations and OH^- against sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) anions.

Compared to Li^+ , a H^+ (whether hydrated or not) is always smaller and therefore assumed to be more mobile. However, there is an enormous difference between the mobilities of H^+ and Li^+ : the mobility of H^+ is almost one order of magnitude higher than that of Li^+ : $36.23 \cdot 10^{-8}$ vs. $4.01 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1}$. Similar observations have been made for the relative OH^- and SO_4^{2-} mobilities. Although these anions have comparable diameters in hydrated form, the mobility of OH^- is considerably higher than that of SO_4^{2-} ($20.64 \cdot 10^{-8}$ vs. $8.29 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1}$, respectively). Note that the aforementioned values are based on non-diffusive ion transport. The behaviour of H^+ in water is described by the Grotthuss mechanism, in which a H^+ from a hydronium ion 'diffuses' through a hydrogen bond to another water molecule (as schematized in Fig. 1). An analogous mechanism for OH^- has been invoked [51,52] to explain high mobility of this anion.

The number of solvated cations and anions depends on the solution pH, which in turn affects the mobility and affinity of these ions to solvent molecules. Therefore, it is reasonable to investigate ionic fluxes under various pHs.

Measuring the height change of an electrode during EC operation is expected to be extremely useful for describing ongoing processes at the electrode/electrolyte interface. The dilatometric measurements can be made in both electrochemical capacitor and battery research [16,43,56-60]. The device is suitable for aqueous and organic electrolytes and for most of the electrode materials used in energy storage devices. It needs to be highlighted that this device can operate in a two-electrode setup, showing the electrode height change during the cell operation, but also the electrodes can be polarized at the selected potential range – then it is a three-electrode setup. There are also some limitations of this technique. First of all, during the electrochemical test it is possible to observe changes of one electrode only. So even if the cell operates in two-electrode configuration, registered dilatation is related only to the 'breathing' of the working electrode. If one is interested in both electrodes, it is necessary to plan another experiment and polarize the cell to the opposite voltage. In such a cell the working electrode will be polarized positively first and then – negatively. As a result, the changes of both electrodes can be recorded. The next thing is that one can monitor only the height changes of the electrodes during ECD experiments. It means that there is no information about what happens at the electrode surface – some ions can penetrate the material pores but also, they can be stored at the surface only. Hence, ECD is not sufficient to determine the EC charging mechanism in detail. As previously discussed, step potential electrochemical spectroscopy (SPECS), developed by Donne and Dupont, can be used to resolve the current and capacitance into several components related to electric double-layer (EDL) formation, ion diffusion, and other residual processes [61,62]. Hence, SPECS data can be used in conjunction with dilatometry results to

Fig. 1. Diameters of selected bare and solvated ions and corresponding mobilities [53–55]; the mechanism of H^+ transfer is based on Grotthuss theory.

identify and quantify the ions responsible for EDL formation at the surface of a porous material and within the pores. Thus, the combination of these techniques enables the calculated diffusion parameter to be correlated with the observed ionic fluxes [20].

Results from *operando* electrochemical dilatometry experiments coupled with SPECS are presented in this paper. These two techniques were applied to better understand and describe fundamental aspects of the behaviour and solvation effect of cations and anions for electrolytes with various pHs. The results of this study provide useful information for the development of energy storage and conversion devices.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Electrode material and electrolyte

An activated carbon (AC) YP-80 F (Kuraray®; Japan) was used as the electrode material for the electrochemical tests. The AC (97%) was mixed with a binder (3%) – 60% polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) solution in water (Sigma Aldrich®; USA) in an ethanol solvent (96%; POCH®; USA). The slurry was mixed at an elevated temperature (70°C) until the solvent evaporated. The powder was then wet with ethanol and rolled into a film with a thickness of 250 µm. Electrodes with a diameter of 10 mm (~9 mg) were cut and dried at 120°C for 8 hr.

The electrodes were characterized using N₂ adsorption-desorption at 77 K (ASAP 2460; Micromeritics®; USA). The specific surface area of the electrodes was calculated using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) equation, and two-dimensional nonlocal density functional theory (2DNLDFT) was used to determine the pore size distribution of the material [63,64].

The electrode behaviour was investigated in several aqueous solutions: 1 mol L⁻¹ lithium sulfate (Li₂SO₄; ≥98%; Sigma Aldrich®; USA) with different pHs (6, 9, and 12) and in 1 mol L⁻¹ lithium hydroxide (LiOH; ≥98%; Sigma Aldrich®; USA) with a pH of 12. The electrolytes were prepared by dissolving the Li₂SO₄ or LiOH in water. The initial pH (9) of Li₂SO₄ was adjusted to pH 6 with sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄; 95%; POCH®; USA) and to pH 12 with LiOH.

The pH of the electrolytes was measured using an S220 SevenCompact pH metre (a relative accuracy ±0.002; Mettler Toledo™; USA) at ambient temperature.

2.2. Electrochemical dilatometry

Operando electrochemical experiments were performed using a high-resolution (5 nm) ECD-3-nano electrochemical dilatometer (El-Cell®; Germany) to measure the thickness change of electrodes during polarization. The electrodes were separated by a stiff glass frit and a 0.26 mm-thick GF/A glass microfibre membrane with a pore size of 1.6 µm (Whatman®; UK). Charge-induced height changes of the working electrode were monitored. Note that the glass frit was fixed in place to ensure that the dimensional change of the counter electrode did not affect the measurement. The experiments were performed using a two-electrode configuration with an AC YP-80F-based *quasi* reference electrode (hereinafter denoted as AC). In preparation for the electrochemical tests, the cell was maintained at a constant voltage for 6 hr to obtain a stable baseline. The electrode height change is expressed as a percentage basis of the thickness or as a direct micrometric change.

2.3. Electrochemical protocols

A computer-controlled multichannel potentiostat/galvanostat VMP3 (BioLogic®; France) was used to perform electrochemical investigations. The experiments were controlled by EC-Lab® software (BioLogic®; France).

2.3.1. Electrochemical techniques

Electrochemical studies were carried out using cyclic voltammetry

(CV) at 1 mV s⁻¹ for a two-electrode configuration and 0.5 mV s⁻¹ for a three-electrode configuration. Large amplitude sinusoidal voltammetry (LASV) was used to obtain detailed information. For this technique, the scan rate is determined by the applied frequency. The frequency (0.15 mHz) was adjusted to reproduce the scan rate applied in CV because dilatometric changes depend strongly on the scan rate.

2.3.2. Raman spectroscopy

Operando Raman spectroscopy was incorporated as a supporting technique for ECD. Spectra were recorded on a DXR-2 computer-controlled Raman microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific®; USA) with a 532 nm wavelength laser (the power was adjusted to 8 mW) within a wavenumber range of 100 – 3565 cm⁻¹.

An experiment was carried out in a typical three-electrode cell containing excess electrolyte. A quartz crystal electrochemical cell was assembled with a 5 mm diameter AC as the working electrode, a platinum wire as the counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl electrode as the reference electrode. The examined AC electrode was placed behind a quartz glass window on the gold current collector and exposed to the laser beam. During the LASV experiment, Raman spectra were recorded every 2.5 min. at a frequency of 0.21 mHz.

2.3.3. Step potential electrochemical spectroscopy

SPECS experiments were carried out in the assembled ECD containing 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ solutions with pHs of 6 and 12 as electrolytes. To pretreat the electrode and determine the potential of an individual electrode (E_{min} and E_{max}), three CV cycles between the cell voltages of 0 – 1.6 V and 0 – -1.6 V (1 mV s⁻¹) were carried out. E_{max} and E_{min} were measured as +0.53 and -1.08 V vs. AC for the electrolytes with pH 6 and +0.43 and -1.17 V vs. AC for the solution with pH 12. The system was held at E_{min} for 30 min before the SPECS measurement to stabilize the current response. Afterwards, SPECS was performed on one electrode over the full, previously determined potential range. The potential was initially set at E_{min} and gradually increased by 10 mV and held for 300 s at each potential step. The system was then polarized in the opposite direction. Five full charge/discharge cycles were performed.

3. Results and discussion

To determine how the pH affects the EC characteristics (the operating potential of the electrodes, current response, and capacitance), the cells containing 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ solutions with different pHs were charged to 1.6 V. The operating potential of the negative and positive electrodes was determined using a two-electrode configuration. The working electrode was then polarized over a given potential range using the three-electrode configuration with the CV technique (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 shows the hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂) evolution potentials (HEP and OEP, respectively) calculated using the Nernst equation. However, these calculated values are only valid for the electrochemical equilibrium state and can shift slightly under an applied polarization. Local changes in the pH during electrode polarization can also significantly affect the calculated HEP and OEP values [65].

The rest potential (OCP) depends strongly on the solution pH – thus, the OCP for the electrolyte with pH 12 is considerably shifted towards lower potentials in comparison to that for the electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9. This shift does not directly follow the trend of 59 mV/pH decade but is in agreement with the Pourbaix diagram and water stability potentials – the higher the electrolyte pH is, the lower the OCP is expected to be [66].

Comparable current responses are obtained for the negatively polarized electrode (Fig. 2a) using electrolytes with pHs 6 and 9, and no rapid increase in the current is recorded although the HEP has been exceeded. The voltammogram deviates slightly from the ideal rectangular shape in both cases, indicating that electrostatic charge accumulation mainly occurs. It is assumed that no redox reactions related to the H₂ storage process occur due to the high overpotential of H₂ evolution

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms (0.5 mV s^{-1}) recorded for an electrode polarized negatively (a) and positively (b) in sulfate-based electrolytes with different pHs and an LiOH solution.

under these conditions. This result once more suggests that the pH increases near the (polarized) electrode. The voltammogram of the electrode operating in the solution with pH 12 exhibits a different character. The current increases right from the beginning of charging, and the slope change is below -1.0 V vs. AC , which agrees with the calculated HEP for this electrolyte (-0.93 V vs. AC); thus, H_2 reduction can be considered in this case. The behaviour of the electrode in 1 mol L^{-1} LiOH solution was investigated as a comparison. As the hydroxide-based EC could not be polarized up to 1.6 V (due to electrolyte decomposition), experiments were performed up to a cell voltage of 1.4 V . The voltammogram is analogous to that recorded for the electrode operating in the sulfate-based electrolyte with a pH of 12, indicating a similar charge storage mechanism. However, the change in the slope during charging is different – the current increases at a higher potential, despite the narrower potential range.

In the case of positive polarization (Fig. 2b), the current increases at potentials higher than $+0.3 \text{ V vs. AC}$ using the electrolyte with pH 6. This result is specific to this case because the operating potential of the electrode ($+0.48 \text{ V vs. AC}$) is below the OEP ($+0.66 \text{ V vs. AC}$). This result indirectly indicates a remarkable increase in the local pH during polarization that shifts the equilibrium potential. The OEP is exceeded using the solutions with pH 9 and 12; however, there are no discernible peaks in the CV profiles recorded for these electrodes. Apart from the increase in the current using the electrolyte with pH 6, the data obtained using electrolytes with pHs 6 and 9 are comparable. A different voltammogram shape is obtained using the electrode operating in the alkaline sulfate solution and the hydroxide-based electrolyte. The OCP values are clearly shifted, but the recorded current is also lower, suggesting a lower capacitance. For the cell containing the LiOH solution, there is a rapid increase in the current above $+0.25 \text{ V vs. AC}$ (just after the OEP is exceeded) and a discernible response during discharging, that is, the measured current increases below -0.1 V vs. AC . The presented data indicate similar charge storage mechanisms for electrodes operating in sulfate-based electrolytes with pHs 6 and 9. Thus, similar ion movement and electrode behaviour can be assumed in the alkaline electrolyte to those observed in the LiOH electrolyte. The dilatometry data are expected to substantiate this assumption.

The dilatation changes vs. the potential are presented in Fig. 3. Note that the presented dilatation is a relative value. The zero of the change in the electrode height change is set at the same potential (0 V vs. AC) for the data presented below.

As the largest differences in the changes in the electrode height are observed for electrodes operating in electrolytes with pHs of 9 (Fig. 3a) and 12 (Fig. 3b), these two cases are compared (a detailed description of the electrode behaviour in these systems is provided below along with LASV results). The electrode expansion under polarization from the OCP

Fig. 3. Change in the electrode height as a function of the applied potential for electrodes that are polarized negatively (blue curves) and positively (red curves) in 1 mol L^{-1} Li_2SO_4 with pHs of (a) 9 and (b) 12, as well as in (c) 1 mol L^{-1} LiOH.

down to lower potentials was recorded, assuming a permselective mechanism with cation insertion (the anion volume: cation volume ratio is denoted as $0:V_c$). However, different trends in the change in the electrode height are observed for the two electrolytes. In the case of the solution with pH 9, the electrode height increases linearly down to -0.6 V vs. AC with a slope of 53%; the electrode expands even faster below this potential with a slope of 90. This result suggests that small cations (H_3O^+) first penetrate the material pores and bulkier cations (solvated Li^+) then contribute to the charge balance at the electrode. This result can also be explained in terms of the material texture. The pore channels may be widest at the pore entrances; hence, both Li^+ and H_3O^+ can easily move into the electrode pores, without producing a remarkable change in the electrode height. However, decreasing the potential pushes the ions deeper into the narrow channels, increasing the electrode expansion rate. The hysteresis loop indicates that the electrode

height increases despite the polarization change, suggesting a delayed ion response to the polarization change. The mechanism for the expulsion of positively charged ions from the material pores with increasing potential appears to be similar to that observed during electrode charging: the electrode height shrinks strongly at the beginning when the larger cations move out of the narrow pore channels and changes mildly closer to the OCP. All changes are reversible over the applied potential range.

When the electrode is polarized from the OCP to higher values, shrinkage of the electrode is still observed, indicating that ions leave the pores. No change in the electrode volume was recorded over the potential range from -0.1 to +0.15 V vs. AC. This result suggests that cations are continuously evacuated from the material and anions simultaneously enter the pores, where the cation and anion volume is balanced ($V_a = V_c$). This phenomenon is called ion exchange. Electrode expansion is observed upon further increasing the potential. However, considering that the anions and cations in the electrolytic solution are at least comparable in size to $\text{SO}_4^{2-} \approx \text{OH}^- \approx \text{H}^+$ and that only Li^+ is slightly larger than the other ions leads to the expectation of similar dilatations for the two polarizations. However, there is a notable difference in the change in the electrode height recorded under negative and positive polarizations -0.64% vs. 0.09%; the rate of the change in the electrode height is also smaller for the positive polarization than for the positive polarization (27% vs. 53%). Here, we postulate that above +0.15 V vs. AC, the adsorption of anions at the electrode produces an increase in the electrode height, but cations are still expelled from the material ($V_a > V_c$). The proposed mechanism is in agreement with that described by Wang *et al.* for an IL electrolyte [27]. The charge was calculated for the charging process from the OCP to negative potentials and, separately, to positive potentials. The change in the electrode thickness could therefore be correlated with the accumulated charge. The results are presented in Fig. S1a. It is seen that the more charge accumulated in the cell the bigger the electrode dilatation. The shape of the curves is in accordance with the dilatation presented vs. the potential applied. The dilatometry data recorded for the electrode operating in the alkaline electrolyte (Fig. 3) indicate different charge storage mechanisms from those postulated on the basis of the voltammograms. Specifically, electrode expansion is observed (0: V_c) during polarization from the OCP towards negative potentials. Note, however, that the potential at which the electrode height starts to increase is considerably above the OCP. To facilitate comparison with the results discussed above, the negative polarization is henceforth considered from the same potential as that for the electrolyte with pH 9, i.e., -0.22 V vs. AC. Continuous electrode expansion was measured in the analyzed potential range. The electrode thickness increases linearly at -0.65 V vs. AC, with a slope of 60%. Below this potential, the electrode expansion rate is even higher – the curve slope is 90%. These values are comparable to those calculated for the electrolyte with pH 9. However, there is no pronounced hysteresis loop. There is a smaller increase in the electrode height after the change in the polarization direction. This result suggests that the cations move out of the carbon pores more easily at high pHs than at low pHs.

During polarization of the electrode towards higher potentials, electrode shrinkage is observed at a constant rate between -0.65 V and -0.15 V vs. AC. Unlike the data obtained at pH 9, there is no plateau in the data obtained at pH 12 – the electrode volume decreases with increasing potential. Therefore, there is no discernible ion exchange region over which the volume of adsorbed anions is equal to that of desorbed cations ($V_a = V_c$). The change in the electrode height above -0.15 V up to +0.44 V vs. AC can be described using a second-degree polynomial with a minimum at +0.37 V vs. AC. Up to this potential, evacuated cations are considered to be responsible for balancing the charges at the positively polarized electrode ($V_a < V_c$). The measured electrode volume increases at potentials higher than +0.37 V vs. AC; therefore, anions are mainly considered to contribute to EDL formation ($V_a > V_c$).

In addition, electrode height change vs. charge accumulated is

presented (Fig. S1b-c) electrodes polarized in the electrolytes with pH 12. Again, it is seen that the results for the Li_2SO_4 solution with pH 12 are comparable with the ones for LiOH as the electrolyte. There is an electrode expansion for all the electrolytes, but the rate of this change is different. It can be noticed especially for the negatively polarized electrode. When the electrolyte of pH 9 was used the electrode's dilatation increased faster and faster with increasing charge. For the alkaline electrolytes, the rate of electrode dilatation with charge stored decreased.

As the differences in the electrode behaviour in electrolytes with pHs of 9 and 12 are the most pronounced for positive polarization, it can be concluded that various anions are responsible for charge balancing within the electrode. To identify the ionic fluxes at various pHs, the dilatometric changes recorded in the sulfate-based electrolytes are compared with those recorded in 1 mol L⁻¹ LiOH (Fig. 3c). As previously mentioned, the voltage applied to the cell operating in the LiOH solution was limited to 1.4 V. However, the electrode behaviour is similar to that of the electrode operating in the alkaline Li_2SO_4 solution over the investigated potential range. Electrode expansion is observed under polarization towards potentials lower than the OCP. When the polarization changes, the cations move very quickly out of the pores. There is a smaller shift in the corresponding response than in the previous cases. Under electrode polarization to higher potential values, continuous electrode shrinkage is observed up to the maximum applied potential, suggesting that the volume of adsorbed anions is lower than the volume of cations ($V_a < V_c$). The minimum dilatation was recorded at approximately the same potential as that recorded in the electrolyte with pH 12. The comparative results clearly demonstrate that the same ions participate in electrode charge balancing for both the LiOH and alkaline Li_2SO_4 solutions. The OH^- is present in high concentrations, has a high mobility and is initially attracted to the electrode surface from the electrolyte with pH 12, whereas electrode expansion caused by SO_4^{2-} is observed at relatively high potentials. By comparison, in the electrolyte with pH 9, sulfate anions penetrate into the material pores (as evidenced by the increase in the electrode height) at lower potentials because of the higher $\text{SO}_4^{2-} : \text{OH}^-$ ratio.

The cyclic voltammetry results provide general information on the electrochemical behaviour and volume changes of the polarized electrode at various pHs, showing the similarities and dissimilarities between the electrolytes used. The LASV technique was used to elucidate the charge storage mechanism during polarization.

The LASV technique consists of applying a periodic voltage in the form of a sine wave. The current is simultaneously registered. For an ideal capacitor, the current leads the voltage by $\phi = +90^\circ$. This phenomenon is referred to as a phase shift between the current and voltage. Any deviation from this ideal phase shift indicates changes in the charge storage mechanism. A phase shift approaching 0° indicates an increasingly resistive character (because the voltage and current of a resistor have the same phase) resulting from certain redox processes.

To investigate the impact of the electrolyte pH on the charging mechanism, the electrochemical cell was polarized using a two-electrode configuration from -1.6 V to 1.6 V. The investigated electrode was repolarized to determine its behaviour during both polarizations. Fig. S2 presents the voltage (grey dashed line) and current (red dashed line) over time recorded for the polarized electrode in sulfate-based electrolytes with different pHs. The experimental data for the current was fitted using a sine function (shown as a solid red line), and the phase shift was determined using the equation $y = y_0 + A \cdot \sin(\pi \cdot \frac{x-x_c}{w})$, where y_0 – offset, A – amplitude, x_c – phase shift and w – period.

A variable scan rate is employed in LASV – the higher the cell potential difference is, the lower the scan rate is. Therefore, the redox activity and electrolyte decomposition are determined at a low scan rate at the maximum and minimum applied voltages. As expected, similarities are observed between the results obtained in electrolytes with pHs

of 6 (Fig. S2a) and 9 (Fig. S2b). The deviations in the current curve are qualitatively similar and occur at the same time. The phase shift determined in both electrolytes is 23.5° . The data obtained in the electrolyte with pH 12 (Fig. S2c) also exhibits peaks at the highest cell potential difference. However, these peaks are shifted in time compared to those registered in electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9. The phase shift is 22.4° . For comparison purposes, a commercial EC containing an organic electrolyte was tested under the same conditions, and the phase shift was found to be 20.3° .

As the analysis of the change in the electrode height as a function of the applied voltage/potential provides only a general picture of the underlying processes during AC electrode polarization, the recorded dilatation vs. stored charge for the sulfate-based electrolytes with pHs of 6 (Fig. S3b), 9 (Fig. S3c) and 12 (Fig. S3d) are analyzed. The charge was calculated by integrating the current over time and is presented as an absolute value.

The cell was polarized from 0 V down to -1.6 V and up to 1.6 V, and the cell potential difference over time is presented in Fig. S3a – the stored charge and changes in the electrode height are presented for the negatively and positively polarized electrodes, respectively. The minimum/maximum cell potential differences are marked by the dash-dotted blue/red and grey lines, along with the 0 V line, to facilitate careful data interpretation.

The charge exhibits the same trend regardless of the electrolyte used – that is, the charge clearly increases with the voltage, reaching 160 C g^{-1} in the electrolyte with pH 6 and 170 C g^{-1} in the electrolytes with pHs of 9 and 12 (Fig. S4).

All the investigated systems exhibit comparable characteristics for charge accumulation during charging. However, this process is the slowest in the alkaline electrolyte when the polarization direction is changed. This result suggests that the charge carriers are not easily expelled from the material. Moreover, during discharge, the charge accumulated on the negatively polarized electrode is not fully recovered. There are still 50, 50, and 70 C g^{-1} stored at 0 V in the electrolytes with pHs of 6, 9, and 12, respectively. When the cell is polarized up to 1.6 V, the same charge accumulates on the electrode as for the 'negative' voltage, and a nonzero charge remains in the system at 0 V. The charge loss is related to the redox reactions/electrolyte decomposition, as shown by the specific current curve in the LASV profiles (Fig. S2).

Considering that a comparable quantity of charge is stored at the negatively polarized electrode and the same cations are present in the electrolytic solutions, the dilatometric changes in the different solutions are also expected to be similar. The maximum electrode expansion reaches 0.65 – 0.68% (Fig. S3b, c, and d). However, electrode swelling clearly has a different character in 'neutral' electrolytes compared to alkaline electrolytes. During cell charging from 0 V down to -1.6 V (the beginning of this process is presented in Fig. S3e), the electrode height changes more slowly in the electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9 than in the electrolyte with pH 12 (the slope is 148% vs. 214%). We assume that these differences are caused by the Li^+/H^+ concentration ratio and solvation shell of the cation. The mild change in the electrode height can be attributed to H^+ adsorption. Compared to the larger and slower Li^+ cations, H^+ are present in higher concentrations at lower pH values and have higher mobilities and can therefore reach the electrode surface faster but cause slower electrode expansion. Further negative electrode polarization (beyond -0.9 V) results in a comparable slope for the change in the electrode height to that measured in the electrolyte with pH 12. This result shows that at this cell potential difference, cations of similar diameter contribute to the charge accumulated in the electrode. Just below the minimum voltage, the electrode dilatation is even slightly faster for electrolytes with lower pHs (6 and 9), suggesting that large cations are attracted to the electrode. This result is in agreement with the solvation shell theory of cations at various pH values – the highest solvation occurs at neutral pH. Hence, the solvated Li^+ cation is larger and not as mobile in electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9 as in the solution with pH 12; therefore, Li^+ is the last ion to enter the material pores. The

recorded change in the electrode height in the alkaline electrolyte is linear as long as the charge increases linearly with time. This result suggests that only solvated Li^+ cations penetrate into the electrode pores or that H^+ are attracted to the electrode surface simultaneously with Li^+ and that the recorded dilatation is related to the accumulation of the larger metal cations. When the cells are discharged, the dilatometric response is similar to the charging process; in the case of electrolytes with pHs 6 and 9, cations with high solvation degrees are first expelled from the material, causing a delayed (due to the low ion mobility) but noticeable (due to the ion size) electrode shrinkage. Then, as the potential approaches -0.2 V, the slope of the electrode height curve decreases, indicating that H^+ are moving out of the electrode. The change in the electrode height in the electrolyte with pH 12 is linear in the voltage. When the voltage reaches 0 V, there is a nonzero change in the electrode height, which is related to the stored charge despite the cell being discharged in theory.

During cell polarization towards 1.6 V, the same charge accumulates at the positive electrode as at the negative electrode. Moreover, the charge loss is the same for both electrodes, showing that the charge is well balanced at both electrodes. It is known that anions (here SO_4^{2-} and OH^-) are attracted to the positively polarized electrode to balance the electrode charge. Considering the ion diameter leads to the expectation that the changes in the electrode height should be similar to or slightly lower than that for negative polarization. However, Fig. S3 shows a significant difference in the electrode heights for the two polarities. The increase in the height of the electrode reaches 0.09% and 0.12% in the electrolytes with pHs 6 and 9, respectively, and is even noticeably lower (-0.11%) than the initial value in the electrolyte with pH 12 (reaching almost 0.7% for the negatively polarized electrode). This result could be attributed to a previously reported charging mechanism for the positively polarized electrode, where the charge is first balanced by cation expulsion and counterions are subsequently attracted to the electrode at higher potentials [27].

Herein, the electrode height initially decreases (according to the decreasing charge) with increasing voltage in all the tested electrolytes. The minimum electrode height in mild electrolytes is reached at 0.45 V (pH 6) and 0.37 V (pH 9). Subsequent electrode expansion is observed up to 1.6 V, where similar changes in the electrode height occur in both electrolytes. For the reverse process, electrode shrinkage is observed with decreasing voltage. For both cases, the rates of these changes are comparable (there are small differences that can be related to the natural drift of the ECD or slight temperature variations), and the minimum dilatation is recorded at the same voltage (0.29 V). Taking all the abovementioned results into account, the same anion or anions are considered to realize charge balancing during positive polarization in electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9, confirming the preliminary inferences based on the cyclic voltammetry results.

As already noted, both the electrochemical behaviour and change in the electrode height for the electrolyte with pH 12 are significantly different from those obtained under milder conditions. The LASV results presented in Fig. S3d are consistent with the previously obtained data. Despite the increase in the voltage, electrode shrinkage is recorded up to 1.2 V, reaching -0.12%. With further positive polarization, very small electrode expansion is observed. This slight dilatation may be counter-intuitive considering that charge balance is realized by the anions. However, data recorded at lower pH values and literature reports clearly demonstrate that anions accumulate within material pores [22,37,44, 48]. Recall that the concentration of the highly mobile OH^- ions is unequivocally higher in the alkaline medium (by six orders of magnitude) than in the electrolyte with pH 6. Hence, this anion is considered to realize charge balancing at the positively polarized electrode. The solvated size of the OH^- ion is comparable to that of SO_4^{2-} ; thus, a high degree of OH^- desolvation is inferred. As a consequence, with increasing voltage, bulky lithium ions are expelled from the material and replaced by smaller desolvated OH^- ions, which manifests as prolonged electrode shrinkage. At adequately high voltages, when the SO_4^{2-} ions are attracted

to the electrode and the Li^+ ions are not evacuated from the pores (or not evacuated as fast as at lower voltages), electrode expansion is still discernible. It should also be taken into account that sulfate anions may only be attracted to the electrode surface without causing any electrode swelling. During cell discharge, the processes are reversed – the anions (first SO_4^{2-} and then OH^-) move out from the electrode, and the cations penetrate the pores. The results obtained using the LASV technique are in accordance with the CV data. The current response, as well as the dilatometry results, are comparable over different cycles. To examine the underlying processes from a different perspective, Raman spectroscopy was performed in *operando* mode. As activated carbons are made up of C-C bonds, Raman spectroscopy is sensitive to changes in the orientation of these carbons. Therefore, the most important bands in the Raman spectra for determining changes in the carbon of the electrodes correspond to ordered and defect structures in the material. The G-band ($\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) corresponds to ordered structures and originates from the C-C stretching vibration, whereas the D-band ($\sim 1355 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) corresponds to defect structures and derives from destruction of the graphite lattice and the presence of disordered carbon structures [67,68].

A LASV experiment was performed at a relatively low applied frequency (because of the high resistance of a typical three-electrode cell). The electrode dilatation was simultaneously measured using ECD for the same experimental setup. The experiments were performed in 1 mol L^{-1} Li_2SO_4 with pH 6 over a potential range determined by ECD (from $+0.47 \text{ V}$ down to -1.13 V vs. AC). The potential and the change in the electrode height over time (for one cycle) are presented in Fig. S5a.

The electrode was polarized from the maximum potential to the minimum potential. The trend in the dilatometry results is comparable to that in the previously recorded data (Fig. S3), showing the electrode height changes over a 0.7% range despite the lower sweep rate. Fig. S5b presents the Raman spectra in the form of a so-called heatmap of the polarized electrode (the Raman shift range is limited to $1100 - 1900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to clearly show the changes in the intensities of the D and G bands). This experiment enables changes in the entire spectrum, as well as the intensities of the selected bands, to be monitored over time. The intensities of both the D and G bands change during electrode polarization (Fig. S5c). The ratio of the intensities of these bands clearly changes. However, comparing these changes with the fluctuation in the potential shows a delay in the Raman response. This shift has been ascribed to the Raman signal being more pronounced during desorption of gaseous products than during adsorption [69]. Therefore, in this experiment, all observed changes in the material correspond to the motion of ions out of the pores in the electrode.

Beyond the maximum/minimum potential, the intensity of the G-band increases and the band position changes slightly (Fig. S6), indicating an increase in the spacing of the graphene layers. Moreover, the variations in the band intensity are more noticeable when the electrode is negatively polarized. The change in the D-band position is also significant, showing that the ions are inserted between the graphene layers and that the number of defects in the carbon matrix increases. Hence, comparing the Raman spectroscopy results with the negative polarization results confirms the different charge storage mechanisms. Nevertheless, it has to be kept in mind, that the electrode volume change could affect the focal plan and thus, the results might be affected. This context requires additional study.

The last analysis was performed using the SPECS technique. The results provide information about charge accumulation and ion fluxes in the vicinity of the polarized electrode. The parameters obtained using this technique can thus be correlated with the changes in the electrode height. The fitted curves (I_{fit}) were matched to the experimental current curves (I_{exp} ; registered at each potential step). The total I_{fit} current consists of four components ($I_{fit} = I_p + I_G + I_D + I_R$): the current related to EDL formation in the bulk electrode (porous surface; I_p) and on the outer surface (geometric surface; I_G), the current related to ion diffusion (I_D), and the residual current (I_R) attributed to side reactions. Each component of the current is characterized by different parameters. For the

purpose of this study, we consider the resistance to EDL formation (R ; ohms) and differential capacitances (C ; F). The product of R and C is the time constant (T ; s) for EDL formation. The charge delivered to the system necessary for EDL formation is measured by the normalized diffusion parameter (B ; $\text{A s}^{0.5} \text{ g}^{-1}$). The profiles of the individual parameters are shown in Fig. S7 for five cycles of electrode repolarization over the full potential range (determined during the two-electrode configuration with the reference experiment at 1.6 V) for the systems operating in 1 mol L^{-1} Li_2SO_4 with pHs of 6 and 12. The error (R^2) of fitting curves to the experimentally registered current data in SPECS technique for both systems is very low, because $R^2 > 0.997$ (Fig. S8). Only extreme pH values were considered because of the high similarity in the electrochemical and dilatometric responses registered for the electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 9 (as confirmed by the results shown in Fig. 3). The reproducibility of the results for each cycle is very high for both systems. An identical system response is observed for the given potential. This reproducibility proves that the system remains stable during operation despite the harsh conditions of SPECS experiments.

The data from the first repolarization cycle for both electrolytes are presented as voltammograms (Fig. 4).

The I_{fit} curves perfectly reflect the profiles of the voltammograms represented by I_{exp} . This result indicates a high coefficient of determination. The results obtained in the two electrolytes differ significantly. For the electrolyte with pH 6 (Fig. 4a; a zoom of the data is presented in Fig. S9), the I_G current is a significant portion of I_{fit} . The I_p current makes a significant additional contribution to I_{fit} (which is, however, considerably lower than that of I_G). The surface of the bulk electrode is considerably more developed than the surface remaining in direct contact with the electrolyte. Theoretically, a porous structure should accumulate more charge than a nonporous structure. This phenomenon can be explained by the limited insertion of ions into the electrode bulk caused by the retention of large SO_4^{2-} ions at the entrance to the micropores (on the external electrode surface). Consequently, ions accumulate in the EDL diffusion layer in the mesopores and the I_G response increases. With increasing potential, the current increases at E_{max} , indicating electrolyte decomposition and possible oxygen evolution. The evolution of gaseous oxygen leads to the reorganization of ions in the mesoporous EDL layer and leads to some ions moving from the outer electrode layers into the pores (I_p increases and I_G decreases near E_{max}). The I_R current strongly affects the total I_{fit} . The higher the redox activity is, including electrolyte decomposition, the higher I_R is. This speculation is confirmed by the rapid increase in the current response at E_{max} . Based on our knowledge, previously performed experiments and mathematical considerations, the contribution of I_R to the total I_{fit} decreases as the data recording time decreases at a specific potential step. However, to fit the I_{fit} curves to I_{exp} and obtain satisfactory insight into the behaviour of both systems at a given potential of the electrochemical dilatometer, it was necessary to use five-minute steps. However, both systems are characterized by relatively high stability under these conditions. As mentioned earlier, electrolyte decomposition is only noticeable near E_{max} . However, this potential is still far from the theoretical OEP ($+0.66 \text{ V}$ vs. AC). However, at E_{min} , there are no signs of electrolyte decomposition and H_2 evolution although the HEP has definitely been exceeded (-0.57 V vs. AC). This result indicates a high overpotential for H_2 evolution, suggesting a local pH change (alkalization) during electrode polarization, causing the HEP and the OEP to shift towards lower values. The results are consistent with the voltammograms presented in Fig. 2. Completely different behaviour is observed for the EC operating in the electrolyte with pH 12 (Fig. 4b). Here, the total I_{fit} varies significantly over the entire potential range. Comparing these results against those obtained for the electrolyte with pH 6 shows that electrolyte decomposition is considerably more pronounced at E_{min} and E_{max} . Electrolyte decomposition occurs near the OEP ($+0.30 \text{ V}$ vs. AC) and HEP (-0.93 V vs. AC). The safe operating potential range for this system can be inferred to be narrower than that for the Li_2SO_4 solution with pH 6. Moreover, there is a considerably smaller difference between I_G and I_p

Fig. 4. SPECS results presented as voltammetry profiles for ECs operating in 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ with pHs of (a) 6 and (b) 12.

than that for the aforementioned electrolyte. In this case, there is comparable charge accumulation in the bulk and on the outer surface (excluding the results obtained at the extreme potentials). The decrease in I_G and the increase in I_P lead to the conclusion that much of the available charge penetrates the micropores. This conclusion is consistent with the presence of a large number of small OH⁻ ions that easily penetrate micropores. Similarly, for the electrolyte with pH 6, I_P dominates over I_G at E_{max} and E_{min} , at which more electrolyte decomposition is observed. Note that the total I_{fit} response is dominated by I_R . Additional side reactions are registered throughout the potential range.

Fig. 5 presents the calculated SPECS parameters and the change in the electrode height. To present the results clearly and facilitate interpretation of the data, a common starting point, E_{min} , is chosen (considering the different potential ranges for the electrolytes at various pH values).

The dilatometric response in the electrolyte with pH 6 is reproducible over five cycles of electrode repolarization (Fig. S7a). The dilatometric change (for the first cycle, presented in Fig. 5a as a red curve) is symmetrical – the change recorded from E_{min} to E_{max} appears as a ‘mirror reflection’. This result indicates fully reversible and repeatable ion movement and insertion/deinsertion into/from the material pores. Furthermore, the difference in the electrode height between E_{min} and E_{max} is less pronounced than that recorded during the LASV experiment. This difference is probably caused by deeper penetration of SO₄²⁻ ions into the electrode or a higher number of adsorbed anions during the SPECS experiment compared to the LASV experiment because of a considerably lower scan rate and a longer hold time at the maximum potential.

The dilatometry profile of the electrode polarized in the alkaline electrolyte is also presented in Fig. 5a (green curve). Compared against the dilatometric response presented in Fig. 5b and Fig. S3d, the electrode height increases significantly and relatively sharply close to E_{max} . This increase is caused by the adsorption of SO₄²⁻ ions at an extremely low scan rate (~0.033 mV s⁻¹); therefore, such an increase was not observed when CV or LASV techniques were used with a scan rate of ~1 mV s⁻¹, where charge balancing at the electrode occurred via adsorption of OH⁻ rather than bulky SO₄²⁻. Under these conditions (a very low scan rate, a relatively high potential value, and, consequently, a high driving force), low-mobility SO₄²⁻ can be adsorbed into the pores of the positively polarized electrode. Directing the polarization towards negative values does not produce a symmetric dilatometry response (as observed in the electrolyte with pH 6). Beyond E_{max} , the electrode continuously increases in volume, indicating further adsorption of SO₄²⁻ anions (down to -0.1 V after exceeding E_{max}). The dilatometric response is constant at relatively high potentials, suggesting that sulfate anions can be partially trapped in the pores or that desorption of these anions from the material

is a very slow process, such that there is no significant change in the electrode height. The other possibility is an exchange of equilibrated ions – SO₄²⁻ anions leave the pores and are immediately replaced by partially/completely desolvated Li⁺ cations.

The charge of one divalent anion can be balanced by two monovalent cations, and the size of the sulfate anion is comparable to that of two lithium cations. In the next stage, as the potential approaches E_{min} , a significant change in the height of the electrode is observed, indicating that Li⁺ is adsorbed (as previously discussed). Note that the dilatometric response changes over the cycles and is therefore not fully reproducible (Fig. S7b). If SO₄²⁻ ions are trapped inside the material, a significant loss of charge is expected during discharge of the system. The charge loss is comparable for both polarities for electrolytes with pHs of 6 and 12 (Fig. S4). In this context, the theory of reasonably fast anion/cation exchange is suitable. The nonreproducible change in the electrode height can be related to irreversible changes in the porous texture of the material. Micropores may increase in size, such that the insertion of ions does not have a pronounced effect during ECD experiments. Furthermore, OH⁻ is expected to participate in EDL formation at positive potentials (because the OH⁻ concentration is very high compared that in the electrolyte with pH 6). However, the small diameter of this anion can make the impact of the anion on the dilatometry response difficult to notice.

The resistance R_P (Fig. 5b) and capacitance C_P (Fig. 5c) are directly related and are therefore discussed together. The R_P determined in the electrolyte with pH 6 is strongly disturbed and higher than that obtained in the electrolyte with pH 12. However, the C_P values are considerably lower in the electrolyte with the higher pH. This result confirms the difficulty the large SO₄²⁻ anion has in penetrating the bulk electrode and the effective ease of EDL formation by OH⁻. At the same time, attention should be paid to parameters related to EDL formation on the electrode surface that is easily accessible to the ions (Fig. 5d and e). Compared to the results for the electrolyte with pH 6, the R_G is two times higher and the C_G is two times lower for the electrolyte with pH 12. This result leads to the conclusion that the SO₄²⁻ ions in the electrolyte with pH 6 are attracted to the electrode but remain on the electrode surface (with limited penetration into the pores). The basic criterion for assigning the index ‘P – porous’ and ‘G – geometrical’ to the R and C parameters was the value of the time constant. EDL formation is faster because the electrode surface (a geometric surface) is easily accessible to ions. In the electrolyte with pH 6 (Fig. 5g), T_G is almost constant throughout the polarization range, demonstrating that EDL formation is not disturbed. In the alkaline solution, T_P varies (Fig. 5f) with the driving force for EDL formation, that is, the applied potential. Interpreting T_P is slightly difficult due to large fluctuations in the value measured in the electrolyte with pH 12 (caused by the high noise in R_P for this electrolyte). However,

Fig. 5. Parameters calculated from SPECS data for the first cycle of electrode repolarization over the full potential range (at a maximum voltage of 1.6 V) for the cell containing 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ with pHs of 6 and 12: (a) the change in the electrode height Δh ; (b and d) the porous and geometric resistance R ; (c and e) the differential specific porous and geometric capacitance C ; (f and g) the time constant T for EDL formation in the pores and on the electrode surface, and (h) the specific normalized diffusion parameter B .

based on the trend observed for R_p , the system with pH 12 has a lower T_p than that with pH 6. Significant differences in the values and profiles of the parameter B are observed (Fig. 5h). For the electrode polarized in the electrolyte with pH 6, a considerably higher charge is needed for ion movement/transport to that needed in the electrolyte with pH 12. This result is logical and coherent considering the lower mobilities of Li⁺ and SO₄²⁻ ($4.01 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $8.28 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1}$, respectively) compared to OH⁻ ($20.64 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1}$). This result is particularly related to SO₄²⁻ transport in the electrolyte with pH 6, for which a large increase in the B value at E_{max} is observed. The changes in the parameter B are considerably smaller for the pH 12 solution, which results from the ease of diffusion of highly mobile OH⁻.

4. Conclusions

It has already been demonstrated that the electrochemical performance of carbon electrode operating in a 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ electrolyte depends strongly on the pH. Moreover, it has been reported that there is

significant alkalization of the electrolyte near the electrode during electrode operation. This is explained by the ion separation and sieving effect coming from the carbon porosity.

In our study, we demonstrated that the carbon electrodes operating with 1 mol L⁻¹ Li₂SO₄ electrolyte at pH 12 exhibits similar behaviour to an LiOH-based solution. Moreover, positive and negative polarization of the electrode produce similar dilatometry responses. Measurements of changes in the electrode height using different techniques (CV and LASV) produce the same results under comparable experimental conditions. However, it is shown that the mechanism of charge storage depends strongly on the electrolyte pH; at pHs of 6 and 9, the charge storage processes, and ion transport mechanisms are similar, whereas considerably different processes occur at pH 12, especially during positive polarization. The higher the electrolyte pH is, the higher the OH⁻ contribution to EDL formation. Furthermore, SPECS experiment demonstrated that the interfacial transport of SO₄²⁻ anions requires a very high driving force and their adsorption can irreversibly change the material texture.

Finally, it is shown that the electrochemical capacitor electrodes perform optimally with the electrolyte of pH 6, as the textural changes of the electrode are reversible, even under very harsh conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paulina Bujewska: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Przemyslaw Galek:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Visualization, Investigation, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Krzysztof Fic:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

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